

Kizimkazi Dimbani Mosque, Zanzibar

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Entry tags: Coastal NEC Bantu, Religious Group, Abrahamic, African Religions, Bantoid, Islam, Islamic Traditions, Swahili Religion, Sunni, Sabaki-Swahili, Atlantic-Congo, Benue-Congo, Northeast Coastal Bantu, Volta-Congo, Mombasa-Lamu-Inland Swahili, Northeast Savanna Bantu, East Bantu, Southern Bantoid, Mosque, Narrow Bantu, Language, Swahili (G.40), Religious Place, African Religion, Islam in Africa, Swahili Islam, Coral Limestone Mosque, Islam

The mosque at Kizimkazi Dimbani is located on the island of Unguja (Zanzibar). According to a text inscribed along its northern inner wall, the mosque was constructed by one Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad in 500AH (1107 CE). Along with the dedicatory text are inscribed verses from the Quran. The mosque is important because it is one of the earliest extant mosques still in use this far south along the East African coast. Multiple excavations have taken place at the mosque and its environs, most recently in 2018 by Akshay Sarathi. Sarathi is yet to publish the results of his excavations, but he excavated 13 burials, multiple sherds of imported and local ceramics, shell and glass beads, faunal remains, and floral remains. In 1959, in conjunction with repairs that were conducted at the mosque, Neville Chittick excavated some trenches. He argued that the site was first seriously occupied in the 10th-11th century CE, as evidenced by the presence of sgraffiato ware. The site seems to have been abandoned from the 14th to 18th centuries CE, according to Chittick. The mosque was built atop wattle-and-daub structures that already existed at the site, possibly in association with the freshwater well that lies nearby. The mosque's location may have been chosen because of this well, which could have been considered to have magical properties considering that it provides freshwater so close to the sea. In 1772/73 CE, according to an inscription within the mosque, the structure was repaired and reconstructed, and it seems to have been continuously occupied until the present since its reconstruction. The mosque was associated with some stone structures that may now be demolished. The management of the mosque has been taken over by the Department of Museums and Antiquities of the Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar, with consultation with the local community. However, a management plan is desperately needed to preserve the mosque given its role in the tourist trade and the deleterious effects of climate change on the structure.

Date Range: 1107 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Kizimkazi Dimbani

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Tanzania, Unguja

The site of Kizimkazi Dimbani, Unguja Island, Zanzibar

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Pradines, S. Early Swahili Mosques: The Role of Ibadi and Ismaili Communities, Ninth to Twelfth Centuries.
- Source 2: Horton, M. C., & Clark, C. M. (1985). Archaeological survey of Zanzibar. *Azania: Archaeological Research in Africa*, 20(1), 167-171.
- Source 3: Chittick, H. N. (1960). Preliminary Report on the Excavations at Kizimkazi Dimbani, Zanzibar. Annual Report for.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: None
- Source 1 Description: None
- Source 2 URL: None
- Source 2 Description: None
- Source 3 URL: None
- Source 3 Description: None

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Scientific excavations and surveys were conducted in 1959, 1985, 2018, and 2023

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1959-2023

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: 1959-1961: Neville Chittick, 1985: Horton and Clark, 2018-2023: Sarathi, Alders.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Water source
- Cave

Notes: The site is associated with a well that is considered remarkable because it provides freshwater so close to the sea. Mwanampambe Cave also lies close to the site. While caves like Mwamampambe that

provide freshwater are sacred in Zanzibar, whether there is a connection between the sacredness of the cave and the sacredness of mosque remains uncertain.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Other [specify]: City

Notes: There is a well associated with the mosque, which is located within the settlement of Kizimkazi Dimbani. As such, there are multiple structures associated with the mosque. A tarred road and dirt tracks lead to the mosque.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: The mosque is located in the heart of the settlement of Kizimkazi Dimbani, and was presumably associated with a settlement that has not survived.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is located in the heart of the settlement of Kizimkazi Dimbani.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: But, Kizimkazi Dimbani is a much smaller settlement than the capital of the island, Zanzibar City, and it is often called a "village" rather than a "city"

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The site is located in the heart of the community of Kizimkazi Dimbani. There are multiple houses, hotels, and hospitals located closeby.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: The mosque is rectangular shaped.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Freshwater well, cave

Notes: The mosque is associated with a well which is considered remarkable because it provides fresh water so close to the ocean. It is also located close to Mwanampambe Cave, which perhaps used to be considered sacred.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The other structures associated with the mosque belong to the settlement of Kizimkazi Dimbani.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is associated with a well which is considered remarkable because it provides fresh water so close to the ocean. It is also located close to Mwanampambe Cave, which perhaps used to be considered sacred.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: It could have been that the cave that lies close by was also considered sacred, but whether its sacredness had anything to do with the mosque remain unclear.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both communal and individual Muslim worship

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was first constructed in 1107CE but was rebuilt/repared in 1772 CE.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was first constructed in 1107CE but was rebuilt/repared in 1772 CE.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: The site seems to have been abandoned around the end of the 14th century and the mosque consequently fell into ruin.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: It was likely not destroyed deliberately.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Natural phenomena

Notes: The mosque was first constructed in 1107CE but was rebuilt/repared in 1772 CE. The site was abandoned at the end of the 14th century, which probably led to the mosque falling into ruin.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Notes: The mosque was first constructed in 1107CE but was rebuilt/repared in 1772 CE.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The mosque was first constructed in 1107CE but was rebuilt/repared in 1772 CE.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The mosque is dedicated to the Muslim God. However, given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that other supernatural beings were associated with the mosque.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– I don't know

Notes: The mosque is dedicated to the Muslim God. However, given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that other supernatural beings were associated with the mosque.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: Given Muslim practice, most likely not. However, it is possible that some semi-divine human being was associated with the mosque at some time given the syncretic nature of East African Islam.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: Given Muslim practice, most likely not. However, it is possible that some ancestor was associated with the mosque at some time given the syncretic nature of East African Islam.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Notes: The mosque was constructed by Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad. He could have represented/been a political authority.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: The mosque was commissioned by Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad. Who actually built the mosque is unknown. However, it is most likely that specialist craftspersons were brought to inscribe the text on the wall of the mosque.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Notes: The text within the mosque simply mentions that the mosque was built on the orders of Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad. It is unknown whether the construction of the mosque originated because of divine intervention.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– I don't know

Notes: The text of the mosque simply says that the mosque was built by Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad. It is unknown whether the construction of the mosque (or any structure before it) marked/commemorated the birthplace of a supernatural or human being.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Notes: The text of the mosque simply says that the mosque was built by Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad. It is unknown whether the construction of the mosque (or any structure before it) was due to an event.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Notes: The text of the mosque simply says that the mosque was built by Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad. It is unknown how he funded the construction of the mosque.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: The text of the mosque simply says that the mosque was built by Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad. His motives were likely pious, but remain mostly unknown. It

is possible that the mosque meant to serve as a marker for Muslim traders arriving from further north.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: The mosque likely housed a Quran and perhaps other sacred texts. There are Qurans stored in the mosque at present.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: There is a built well that taps a freshwater spring next to the mosque

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The well is attached to the mosque

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is clearly the dominant structure, and the well plays an ancillary role to it

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

Notes: The mosque itself is a monumental structure.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: The mosque's foundations are sunk into the earth.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Beach sand was likely used in its construction.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: Clay was likely used as a mortar

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: Plaster made by burning limestone or seashells was used as a mortar and to face the mosque.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: The rafters seem to be made of mangrove poles. I don't know if they were sourced locally. We know there was an active trade in mangrove poles along the East African coast because of the wood's use in construction.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Notes: Mangroves may have been more widespread in the environment of Zanzibar than they are at present.

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Limestone blocks were used in the initial construction of the extant mosque structure and in its repair/reconstruction in the 1770s.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Notes: Unguja Island is essentially a giant limestone block.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Paint, fabrics (for the wall and floor)

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The outside of the mosque is painted white

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The inside of the mosque is painted white, but the northern wall (with the mihrab) has been painted orange and black. The inscription, which is located on this wall, is also painted orange and black.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There are movable tapestries, carpets, and prayer mats inside the structure.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

Notes: In accordance with Islamic practice, the decoration is not figural. However, figural decoration could have existed in the past, given that East African Islam is deeply syncretized with local religious practice.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: The decoration consists of a fairly ornate mihrab recessed in the northern wall and accessible through a scalloped arch. The inscription is also written in floriate/plaited Kufic, which is generally geometric but evokes vines and other floral motifs.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: The decoration consists of a fairly ornate mihrab recessed in the northern wall and accessible through a scalloped arch. The inscription is also written in floriate/plaited Kufic, which is generally geometric but evokes vines and other floral motifs.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: The inscription running along the northern wall and into the mihrab is written in floriate/plaited Kufic, which is generally geometric but evokes vines and other floral motifs.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: None.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: The decoration is located within the mosque, but is accessible to all who enter.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: In accordance with Islamic practice, no figural representations are present. However, given that East African Islam has syncretized with local religious tradition, one cannot discount the possibility that statues may have been present in the past.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The inscription is located on a relief running along the northern inner wall of the mosque and into the mihrab.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Notes: But the interior and exterior of the mosque are painted white. The northern wall is painted with different colors. The inscription relief is painted orange and black.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions mention the dedication of the mosque by one Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad, along with verses from the

Quran. They are written in plaited/floriate Kufic, a highly ornamental and difficult to read script.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions mention the dedication of the mosque by one Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad, along with verses from the Quran.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions mention the dedication of the mosque by one Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad, along with verses from the Quran.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The inscriptions mention the dedication of the mosque by one Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad, along with verses from the Quran.

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: There is a scalloped arch framing the entrance to the mihrab.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: Other than the inscription there does not seem to any other iconography associated with the mosque. Its single minaret has some geometric designs but these seem to be primarily decorative.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: But there is an associated cemetery and biers for carrying corpses are stored within the mosque.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: But there is an associated cemetery and biers for carrying corpses are stored within the mosque. Ancestor/spirit veneration is an aspect of Swahili Islam at present, but does not seem to be associated with the mosque.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Notes: But there is an associated cemetery and biers for carrying corpses are stored within the mosque.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: But some of the graves in the attached cemetery have ceramics embedded in them. The embedding of ceramics (especially foreign) in grave stones/markers is a tradition that goes back centuries on the Swahili coast.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: But some of the graves in the attached cemetery have ceramics embedded in them. The embedding of ceramics (especially foreign) in grave stones/markers is a tradition that goes back centuries on the Swahili coast.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: But there is an associated cemetery and biers for carrying corpses are stored within the mosque.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: There is an associated cemetery and biers for carrying corpses are stored within the mosque.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– I don't know

Notes: Multiple members of the same family may be buried in the cemetery, but this does not necessary equate to a family tomb/crypt.

↳ Domestic context:
Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: None

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– No

Notes: While Allah is often described with human-like adjectives, it is important to note that Muslims do not like to anthropomorphize Allah.

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

Notes: Allah is the God of all the universe

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– Yes

Notes: Allah is the God of all the universe.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

Notes: But note that the dedicatory inscription in the mosque asks Allah to grant the builder of the mosque long life and to destroy his enemies. The builder of the mosque may have had elite

status.

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Beneficent, merciful, eternal, most sacred, embodiment of peace, infuser of faith, preserver of safety, might, omnipotent, dominant, creator, evolver, flawless, shaper, great forgiver, all-prevailing, supreme bestower, total provider, supreme solver, omniscient, the elevating one, honor-bestower, abaser, all-hearer, impartial judge, embodiment of justice, knower of subtleties, clement, magnificent, sublime, great, guardian, sustainer, reckoner, majestic, bountiful, watchful, responsive, omnipresent, wise, loving, glorious, infuser of life, all-observing, embodiment of truth, universal trustee, strong, firm, protective, singly laudable, the one to whom the count of all things are known, originator, restorer, maintainer of life, inflictor of death, self-subsisting, perceptive, all-noble, sole god, all-authoritative, expediter, delayer, first, perceptible, imperceptible, exalted, merciful, retaliator, pardoner, benign, sovereign, majestic, honorable, just, gatherer of creation, self-sufficient, distressor, bestower of sufficiency, preventer, bestower of benefits, prime light, provider of guidance, unique, ever-surviving, eternal inheritor, guide to path of rectitude, extensively enduring

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Allah does not communicate with the living at the mosque at present. However, given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is possible that Allah was considered to communicate with the living at this site in the past.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Notes: However, it is possible that in the past previously human spirits were considered to be present at the site given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: However, it is possible that in the past previously human spirits were considered to communicate with the living at the site given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: It is difficult to answer this question for the distant past given that we do not have texts (other than the dedicatory inscription) dealing with the nature of Islam in the region before the 19th century. However, it is entirely possible that nonhuman spirits were considered to be present, seen, and felt at the site.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: It is difficult to answer this question for the distant past given that we do not have texts (other than the dedicatory inscription) dealing with the nature of Islam in the region before the 19th century. However, it is entirely possible that nonhuman spirits were considered to be present, seen, and felt at the site, and were considered to communicate with the living.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Notes: Not at present, but it is difficult to answer this question for the distant past given that we do not have texts (other than the dedicatory inscription) dealing with the nature of Islam in the region before the 19th century. However, it is entirely possible that human-divine beings were considered to be present, seen, and felt at the site.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Not at present, but it is difficult to answer this question for the distant past given that we do not have texts (other than the dedicatory inscription) dealing with the nature of Islam in the region before the 19th century. However, it is entirely possible that human-divine beings were considered to be present, seen, and felt at the site, and considered to communicate with the living.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Worshipping no God other than Allah

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Not at present, but it is possible that in the past people communicated with god(s) or other supernatural beings at this site, given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of Islam in East Africa

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 1-200

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Notes: Islam in the region is rather strict, but still makes room for spirit veneration and other syncretic practices.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Notes: Islam in the region is rather strict, but still makes room for spirit veneration and other syncretic practices.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: By all individuals

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Not at present, but it is possible that pilgrimages to this site took place in the past.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: Not at present, but it is possible that this site was a venue for feasting in the past.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

– specify: Yearly - Ramadhan, the two Eids, Maulid, etc.

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: The mosque can accommodate a couple of hundred people at most

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Notes: Not at present, but divination could have taken place at the mosque in the past.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Notes: Not at present, but healing could have been present/practiced at this place in the past.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: There is a full-time Imam in charge of the site.

↳ Present part time

– No

Notes: The Imam is present full-time

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The Imam is male. However, given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of Islam in East Africa, especially in the past, it is entirely possible that female religious specialists were present.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: The Imam seems to hail from the local community and thus has permanent links to the community. Therefore, he is de facto dedicated to the site for life.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The Imam has his own house with an attached farm.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: I don't know where new Imams are trained to take over after the current Imam.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: A "mosque committee" consisting of the Imam and local men is in charge of the mosque and its maintenance.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: Only the Imam and maybe a couple of assistants are in charge of the mosque.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Notes: The mosque seems to be supported by the local community, but it controls the land on which it sits.

Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Notes: But it lends items like biers to the local community as needed.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Notes: But it could have in the past, given its location and control of the freshwater well.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is located along the main road running through the city.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Religious services

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Quran is stored and read at this place.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: The inscription in the mosque says that the mosque was commissioned by one Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad in 1107 CE.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Imam interprets the Quran for the local community

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Notes: But Quranic verses are part of the inscriptions on the north wall of the mosque.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Kizimkazi Dimbani Mosque, Zanzibar, Flury, S. "The Kufic Inscription of Kizimkazi Mosque, Zanzibar, AD 1107", 1922.

Reference: Kizimkazi Dimbani Mosque, Zanzibar, Chittick, Neville. "Preliminary Report on the Excavations at Kizimkazi Dimbani, Zanzibar", 1960.

Reference: Kizimkazi Dimbani Mosque, Zanzibar, Chami, Maximilian. "Management of Religious Heritage in Tanzania: A Case Study of Kizimkazi Mosque on Zanzibar Island." 14 (2017).